

A SIMPLIFIED APPROACH FOR INTERLAMINAR STRESSES
AROUND A HOLE IN $[\phi/-\phi]_S$ LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

An approximate approach is introduced to determine the interlaminar stresses around a circular hole in $[\phi/-\phi]_S$ laminates under tension. The effect of two parameters, the ratio of hole radius to plate thickness, r_0/h , and the orientation angle ϕ , is investigated. Distribution curves of the three interlaminar stress components along the radial and circumferential directions are presented. The amount of work required here is much less than any other methods available in the literature.

INTRODUCTION

The investigation of interlaminar stresses near the free edges of a composite laminate subjected to in-plane load has attracted many research workers' attention during recent years. However, only a limited number of papers are available on the interlaminar stresses around a hole for $[\phi/-\phi]_S$ laminates [1-3]. Since a 3-D analysis must be considered in the immediate area around a circular hole, the work involved is usually very complicated. A simplified method, proposed by the authors for determining the interlaminar stresses in laminated strips [4], is extended in this paper for the stresses around a circular hole in $[\phi/-\phi]_S$ laminates under in-plane uniform tensile load. Both the equilibrium equations and the boundary conditions are satisfied. This convenient method can be used in a systematic fashion for the evaluation of the effect associated with the different parameters involved.

ANALYSIS

The following assumptions are adopted for obtaining the analytic solution: (1) The length and width of the laminate are much larger than

the hole diameter; (2) the distribution of in-plane stresses is uniform across the thickness of each ply; and (3) The affected area associated with the interlaminar stresses is limited to a distance of twice the laminate thickness from the hole edge. Therefore, the remote stresses in the plate can be evaluated from the classical anisotropic plate theory. But in the region near the hole, a three dimensional stress state is considered. The equilibrium equations for the k^{th} ply given in cylindrical coordinate system can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_r^{(k)}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^{(k)}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}^{(k)}}{\partial z} + \frac{\sigma_r^{(k)} - \sigma_\theta^{(k)}}{r} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^{(k)}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta^{(k)}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}^{(k)}}{\partial z} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}^{(k)}}{r} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}^{(k)}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}^{(k)}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \sigma_z^{(k)}}{\partial z} + \frac{\tau_{rz}^{(k)}}{r} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the origin of the coordinate system is assumed to coincide with the hole center; and $k=1,2,\dots,n$, is measured from the mid-plane of symmetry.

Fig. 1 Coordinate system
and stresses

Assume that $\sigma_r^{(k)}$, $\sigma_\theta^{(k)}$, $\tau_{r\theta}^{(k)}$ be represented by the following power function R_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r^{(k)} &= (1-R_2^4)^{3/2} (\sigma_{r1}^{(k)} - \sigma_{r0}) + \sigma_{r0} \\ \sigma_\theta^{(k)} &= (1-R_2^4)^{1/2} (\sigma_{\theta1}^{(k)} - \sigma_{\theta0}) + \sigma_{\theta0} \\ \tau_{r\theta}^{(k)} &= (1-R_2^4)^{1/2} (\tau_{r\theta1}^{(k)} - \tau_{r\theta0}) + \tau_{r\theta0} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $R_2 = (r_0 + 2h - r)/2h$, for $r_0 \leq r \leq r_0 + 2h$ (3)

is a nondimensional parameter. The stress terms with a subscript "o" are

referred to the in-plane stresses in an orthotropic plate [5], with its elastic moduli determined by the properties of individual layers [6].

We consider that the strains for each ply to coincide with the ones of an anisotropic plate in the remote region of the hole. Therefore, the in-plane stresses for each ply can be calculated from the stress-strain relations. These stresses are designated by a subscript "1" in equations (2).

The boundary conditions are:

(a) On the top and bottom faces of the laminate, $z = \pm h/2$,

$$\tau_{rz} = \tau_{z\theta} = \sigma_z = 0 \quad (4)$$

(b) On the interface between two plies, the interlaminar stresses calculated from the two neighboring plies must be equal; and on the symmetric mid-plane,

$$\tau_{rz} = \tau_{z\theta} = 0 \quad (5)$$

(c) Along the circle, $r = r_0 + 2h$,

$$\sigma_r^{(k)} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(k)} = \tau_{rz}^{(k)} = 0, \quad \tau_{z\theta}^{(k)} \rightarrow \infty \quad (6)$$

(d) Along the hole edge, $r = r_0$

$$\sigma_r^{(k)} = \sigma_{r1}^{(k)}, \quad \sigma_{\theta}^{(k)} = \sigma_{\theta 1}^{(k)}, \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(k)} = \tau_{r\theta 1}^{(k)} \quad (7)$$

Stresses given by expression (2) satisfy the boundary condition (d) and (c), because we have $\sigma_{r_0} = \tau_{r\theta 0} = 0$ along the hole edge, $r_0 = r$. In solving equations (1), boundary condition (a) will be enforced. Note that the following three relations exist, i.e.,

$$h(\sigma_{x_0}, \sigma_{y_0}, \tau_{xy_0}) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^n t^{(k)} (\sigma_{x1}^{(k)}, \sigma_{y1}^{(k)}, \tau_{xy1}^{(k)}) \quad (8)$$

where $t^{(k)}$ is the thickness of the k^{th} layer, and h is the total thickness of the laminate. It will be shown that boundary condition (b) is certainly satisfied. Therefore, the stresses obtained from (1) and (2) satisfy both the equilibrium equations and the boundary conditions.

The computational procedure can be summarized as follows:

(1) Compute the in-plane stresses σ_{j_0} , $j=x,y,s$ of the equivalent orthotropic plate containing a hole; (2) Using the stress-strain relation, then $\sigma_{j1}^{(k)}$ in each ply are obtained from σ_{j_0} ; and (3) Substituting expressions (2) into equations (1), the interlaminar stresses are finally obtained.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Numerical results are obtained for $[\phi/-\phi]_S$ laminates under uniform tensile load p . The following elastic constants of a unidirectional ply are used in the computation: $E_1 = 145.0$ GPa, $E_2 = 10.7$ GPa, $G = 4.5$ GPa, and $\gamma_{12} = 0.31$, where E_1 is the Young's modulus along the fiber direction. The ratio r_0/h is selected from 1, 10, to 100, and the inclination angle ϕ runs from 15° to 75° for every 15° interval. Seven values of θ , namely,

0° , 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° are used in the computation; and finally, the ratio of $(r-r_0)/h$ is assumed from 0.005 to 1 instead of from 0 to 1 in order to avoid the singularity problem for $\tau_{z\theta}$ at $r = r_0$.

Some typical distribution curves of $\tau_{z\theta}$, σ_z and τ_{rz} are presented in Figs. 2 through 7. For comparison purpose, Figure 8 shows the stress distribution along the circumferential direction for the special case, $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_S$ with $r_0/h = 100$, where the solid curves are given by this paper and the dotted lines are taken from [1].

Fig. 2 Distribution of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ around the circular direction

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Results on $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ indicate that this shear stress is much larger at the edge of the hole than any other locations. Its maximum value depends on ϕ , the orientation angle. For example, a maximum occurs at $\theta = 90^\circ$ for $\phi \leq 45^\circ$, also at $\theta = 0^\circ$ for $\phi \geq 60^\circ$. But the most serious case is for $\phi = 30^\circ$. As the ratio r_0/h increases, so is the ratio of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$. However, when r_0/h is equal to or greater than 10, the maximum value of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ seems to have reached asymptotical peaks as shown in Table 1. On the other hand, the distribution of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ along the radial direction is not primarily related to r_0/h . Its magnitude diminishes quickly as one moves outward from the

edge of the hole with a distance of about one laminate thickness. The ratio of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ usually turns out to be less than 0.25 for the portion where the radial distance from the hole edge exceeds 0.5 h .

TABLE 1
Maximum values of $\tau_{z\theta}/p$ for different ϕ and r_0/h

ϕ		15	30	45	60	75
$(\tau_{z\theta}/p)_{\max}$	$r_0/h=1$	1.24	2.11	1.38	1.30	0.64
	10	1.81	2.25	1.38	1.52	1.12
	100	1.88	2.26	1.38	1.54	1.18

The normal stress ratio σ_z/p also has its maximum along the edge of the hole except for the case where $\phi = 75^\circ$ with $r_0/h = 1$. But for the case where r_0/h is less than 1, $(\sigma_z/p)_{\max}$ varies greatly along the circumferential direction and strongly depends on ϕ . For $r_0/h \geq 10$, its distribution along the radial and circumferential directions does not seem to depend upon the ratio r_0/h anymore, but the orientation angle ϕ . For $\phi < 45^\circ$, $(\sigma_z/p)_{\max}$ does not appear to be higher than 0.15; but it turns out to be greater than 1.60 for $\phi = 75^\circ$. Its magnitude diminishes rapidly along the radial direction for one laminate thickness distance from the hole edge.

The value of τ_{rz} is usually smaller than the other two interlaminar stress components. It only extends about a distance of $2h$ from the hole edge. Its maximum value and location depend upon the ratio r_0/h as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5 Distribution of σ_z/p around circular direction ($r_0/h=1$)

Fig. 6 Distribution of σ_z/p around the radius direction

Fig. 7 Distribution of τ_{rz}/p around the radius direction

The distribution of three interlaminar stresses along the circumferential direction are plotted for $[45/-45]_S$ carbon/epoxy laminate with a r_0/h ratio equal to 100. The corresponding dotted curves are obtained from [1]. For $(\tau_{z\theta}/p)_{\max}$, the results given by the two methods are in very good agreement. For τ_{rz}/p , the distribution pattern is similar but the magnitude differs somewhat. The distribution of σ_z/p has a substantial difference between the results. From the physical point of view, the distribution of σ_z is antisymmetrical to $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$, so the value of σ_z should be equal to zero at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$.

Based on the results obtained, the following conclusions can be made:

- (1) A singular nature exists for $\tau_{r\theta}$ and σ_z along the hole edge, but the magnitude diminishes rapidly. On the other hand, τ_{rz} is usually less than the other two interlaminar stresses with a maximum occurring in the region between $0.2h$ and $0.5h$ from the edge of the hole; (2) For $r_0/h \geq 10$, the distribution and magnitude of all stresses are basically the same. The

Fig. 8 Distribution of three stresses around the circular direction
 ($[45/-45]_s$, $r_0/h=100$)

results for the case with $r_0/h = 10$ can therefore be used for other cases where $r_0/h > 10$; and (3) In the region where $30^\circ < \phi < 60^\circ$, the interlaminar stresses are lower than any other portion. They assume a minimum for $\phi = 45^\circ$.

A simplified approach presented in this paper has been demonstrated successfully to be capable in computing the interlaminar stresses around a circular hole in any symmetric laminate. It is convenient to investigate in a systematic fashion in regard to the effect of different parameters involved. The procedure is much simpler than any other methods available in the literature, and the results are useful for engineering design purposes.

REFERENCES

1. Tang, S., Interlaminar stresses around circular cutouts in composite plates under tension. *AIAA Journal.*, 1977, 15, 1631-1637.
2. Rybicki, E.F. and Schmueser, D.W., Effect of stacking sequence and lay-up angle on free edge stresses around a hole in a laminate plate under tension. *J. of Composite Materials*, 1978, 12, 300-311.

3. Carlsson, L., Interlaminar stresses at a hole in a composite member subjected to in-plane loading. J. of Composite Materials, 1983, 17, 238-249.
4. Ueng, C.E.S. and Zhang, K.D., A simplified approach for inter-laminar stresses in orthotropic laminated strips. J. of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 1985, 4, 273-286.
5. Lekhnitskii, S.G., Anisotropic Plates, English edition, translated by Tsai, S.W. and Cheron, T., Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, New York, 1968.
6. Tsai, S.W. and Hahn, H.T., Introduction to Composite Materials, Technomic Pub. Co., 1980.